

Effect of Grate Opening Size on Vertical Displacement Behavior in FOPS Add-On Structures: A Finite Element Study

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Abstract

Operator safety in construction machinery is ensured through various standards. Among these, the FOPS (Falling Object Protective Structure) and ROPS (Roll Over Protective Structure) standards play a critical role in cabin safety. While ROPS focuses on protecting the operator against machine rollover, FOPS addresses the cabin's resistance to falling objects. FOPS standards and analyses are especially vital in environments such as mining and forestry, where there is a high risk of objects falling onto the cabin roof. There are two different FOPS levels in the relevant standard. Those levels have different falling object geometries and energy requirements.

In this study, the mechanical behavior of auxiliary protective structures with grated designs, intended to be installed on top of cabins, was investigated and compared under Level 2 impact load. The effect of varying grate spacing on the structure's response to falling objects was examined. The influence of grate spacing on vertical displacement was analyzed using the finite element software MSC Marc, and the results were interpreted accordingly.

Keywords: Construction Machinery; FEM; FOPS; Operator Safety

1. Introduction

Ensuring operator safety is a fundamental concern in the construction machinery industry. Machines used in harsh environments such as mining, forestry, and heavy construction are often subject to extreme working conditions that pose significant risks to both the operator and the equipment. As a result, international safety standards have been developed to minimize these risks and enhance operator protection.

Two of the most important safety standards for construction machinery cabins are the ROPS (Roll Over Protective Structure) and FOPS (Falling Object Protective Structure). While ROPS focuses on protecting the operator during rollover events, FOPS addresses the resistance of the cabin against impacts from falling objects. These standards are defined by ISO 3471:2008 [1] and ISO 3449:2005 [2], respectively, and provide strict guidelines for structural testing and performance evaluation.

The FOPS standard, in particular, is critical for machines operating in environments with a high likelihood of falling debris, such as forests or excavation sites. It defines two protection levels, each associated with different object geometries and impact energy values. The structural integrity of the cabin or any additional protective element must be sufficient to absorb the impact energy without compromising operator safety.

In the ISO 3471:2008 standard, falling objects that may impact the cabin are represented at two different levels. The sizes of the falling objects for Level 1 and Level 2 are shown in Figure 1, while the expected impact energy these objects exert on the cabin is presented in Table 1.

Figure 1. Falling Objects for FOPS, Level 1 (a) and Level 2 (b)

Table 1. Impact Energies Comparison on Different FOPS Levels

	Level 1	Level 2
Expected Impact Energy	1360 J	11600 J

S355 is used as material. Material properties are shared in Table 2 below.

Table 2. S355 Material Properties

Young Modulus (GPa)	210
Poisson Ratio	0.3
Yield Strength (MPa)	355

Over the years, several studies have focused on the structural behavior of FOPS components. Previous research has explored various materials, modeling techniques, and structural reinforcements to improve performance. Gomathinayagam et al. [3], modeled falling objects as rigid bodies so the deformation behavior of the falling object is removed from the analysis. Pai [4] compared steel and composite materials in terms of protective capability. Gheorghe et al. [5] used static calculated forces to simulate impact model instead of a dynamic falling object contact. By doing so, they aimed to lower the analysis solution time and acquire more accurate results. Kocabıyık K.R. [6], studied on changing the top shell thickness of the design and compared the results on his master thesis. Before doing the impact analysis, he made a modal analysis to find the weak spots of the design and later on he reinforced those weak areas. Al-Bassit et al. [7] studied on alternative falling object protective structure designs with finite element method. Their main objective in the study is to drop the object to the weakest point of the structure and obtain vertical displacement values, and by comparing the results finding the most successful design. Hallén and Hjorth [8] conducted a study using FEA software to reduce time and cost in FOPS analyses, validating their results with physical tests. They incorporated material data from tensile tests to improve the accuracy of nonlinear simulations and made design modifications based on analysis outcomes. They recommended final physical testing of the model for reliability.

In this study, the mechanical behavior of grated auxiliary protective structures mounted on FOPS systems was investigated using numerical methods. The central hypothesis is that increasing the spacing between grates reduces the structure's resistance to falling objects, thereby resulting in greater vertical displacement values. To evaluate this hypothesis, designs with varying grate spacings were analyzed using the finite element method in MSC Marc software, and the structural responses were comparatively assessed based on the simulation results. Although there are various studies in the literature focusing on the overall strength of FOPS structures, the effect of grate spacing in grated designs has not been directly addressed. This study aims to fill that gap and is expected to contribute to the optimization of engineering decisions during the design process.

2. Materials and Methods

In this section, the methods used for the computational structural analysis of various FOPS designs are presented in detail. The finite element model of the grated protective structure was created using MSC Apex, which was used for geometry definition and meshing. A Level 2 falling object, defined by the ISO 3449:2005 standard, was selected, and the falling distance was set to 2 meters. A general overview of the study's workflow is presented in the flowchart shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Methods flow chart

2.1. CAD Models

The main objective of this study is to investigate how varying gap openings in grated protective structures affect the vertical displacement results under impact loading. To conduct this investigation, six different CAD models featuring different gap widths were created using SpaceClaim. These variations allow for a comparative analysis of how structural openness influences mechanical response during a falling object scenario. The design details and names of each model are presented in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. CAD Models

All of the examined models include curved sheet metal components. These components are formed by assembling vertical and horizontal parts, which will be joined together using welding techniques. Model A1 and Model B1 contain fewer upper horizontal sheets compared to Model A and Model B, respectively. Similarly, Model A2 and Model B2 include fewer lower vertical sheets than Model A and Model B. The structure consisting of the upper horizontal sheet, lower vertical sheet, and curved sheet metal is shown in detail in Figure 4 through Model B.

Figure 4. Model B isometric view (a), Upper horizontal curved sheet (b), Lower vertical straight sheet (c)

To better understand the design model, the side and front views are presented in Figure 5. The upper sheets are modeled with a curved profile featuring an arc angle of 30° , whereas the bottom sheets are flat but positioned along a curved path with a radius corresponding to an angle of 26.6° .

Figure 5. Side view (up) and front view (down)

The effect of the spacing between grids on vertical displacement during the impact analysis constitutes the main focus of

this study. A visual representation of the naming convention for the gap distances is provided in Figure 6, while the specific distance values for each model are presented in Table 3.

Figure 6. Gap naming

Table 3. Gap distance values for each model

	Model A	Model A1	Model A2	Model B	Model B1	Model B2
d1 (mm)	32	32	72	72	72	152
d2 (mm)	32	72	32	72	152	72

2.2. Finite Element Method

Solution of a such system by analytical methods would require differential equations. It is not always possible to solve partial differential equations especially if the system is complex. The finite element method is a good way to approximate the solution. There are approximately 10 different element types exist in finite element method. The most commonly used ones are linear quadrilateral, quadratic quadrilateral, linear hexahedron and quadratic hexahedron elements. [9]. The finite element model was created in MSC Apex. Linear quadrilateral element type was chosen to reduce the solution time. The difference in terms of the number of nodes between linear and quadratic quadrilateral elements is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Linear quadrilateral element (a) and quadratic quadrilateral element (b) nodes

To reduce the analysis time, the mass dropped on FOPS is moved to the location where it starts contacting the structure. By doing that, the time required for falling object to travel to reach the FOPS is eliminated from the analysis. The object has a speed when it reaches the FOPS. This speed value is calculated and used as an initial condition in the analysis. Initial height

and the mass of the falling object are known. By using the conservation of energy formula, and transforming the potential energy to kinetic energy, velocity can be calculated for the moment object contacts the body.

In this study, large deformation formulation was utilized to accurately simulate the nonlinear mechanical response of the protective cabin structures under FOPS impact loading. The finite element analyses were carried out using the Updated Lagrangian approach, where the equilibrium equations are formed with respect to the current configuration. For the isotropic elasto-plastic material model defined in the simulation, MSC Marc internally assigns a multiplicative decomposition scheme to represent the elastic behavior, while an additive decomposition is employed for the plastic part. This hybrid formulation enables the software to evaluate large strain effects more realistically by handling elastic deformation through deformation gradients and plastic deformation through incremental strain components [10]. Such an approach provides increased numerical stability and physical consistency in highly nonlinear impact simulations.

Segment to segment (STS) contact algorithm is used in this analysis. STS method provide improved stability and energy conservation in large strain impact simulations Segment-to-segment contact formulations appear applicable in large-strain finite element models, particularly when applied to impact problems [11]. Puso et al. [11] and Recuero and Lindsay [12] report that segment-to-segment approaches improve numerical stability, eliminate locking, and better preserve energy under large deformations. On the other hand, Metzger and Dubey [13], as well as Recuero and Lindsay [12], note that node-to-segment formulations yield comparable stress responses in dynamic impact scenarios.

2.3. Results

Maximum vertical displacement results after the impact for each model is shared in detail and compared. It was also observed that there is no fracture occurring on any of the models. It was observed by checking plastic strain values on each model. None of the values exceeded the plastic strain value when the material fails. No additional fracture mechanics analysis was done.

Vertical displacement contours for Model A group and Model B group are shared in Figure 8 and Figure 9. Each legend lower limit is set as -80mm, by doing so visual comparison is possible.

Figure 8. Vertical displacement contours of model group A

Figure 9. Vertical displacement contours of model group B

Maximum vertical displacement values for each model are shared graphically in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Maximum displacements on all models

The table below presents the maximum permanent vertical deformation values observed in the analyzed models, along with the total energy at the peak elastic and plastic strain, and the plastic strain energy values alone.

Table 4. Numerical results for each model

	Maximum Plastic Displacement (mm)	Maximum Elastic + Plastic Strain Energy (J)	Plastic Strain Energy (J)
Model A	24	4141	2544
Model A1	27.9	4288	3185
Model A2	33.8	4322	3255
Model B	40.3	3377	2166
Model B1	52.4	3441	2432
Model B2	79.9	4612	3605

Total strain energy and displacement graphs are given below for comparison. Figure 11 shows total strain energy for each model, while figure 12 shows displacements. Time has chosen as 0.15 seconds, the time when the falling object bounces back and all the models start to stabilize.

Figure 11. Total Strain Energy Comparison for t=0.15s

Figure 12. Displacement Comparison for t=0.15s

In addition to the previously conducted studies, an alternative approach was explored in which the thicknesses of the sheets in Model B were increased with the aim of achieving the vertical displacement values observed in Model A. This analysis was carried out using the finite element software Marc Mentat. As a result, it was observed that increasing the thicknesses of the vertical and horizontal sheets in Model B by 81.25% led to vertical displacement values comparable to those obtained in Model A. A comparison of the vertical displacement distributions is presented in Figure 11.

Figure 13. Model A and thicker Model B comparison

When the thicknesses of the vertical and horizontal sheets in Model B were increased by 81.25% to improve its vertical displacement performance closer to that of Model A, the total material weight reached 103 kg, compared to 114 kg for Model A. Based solely on raw material costs, this modification makes Model B a more economical and feasible option. It should be noted, however, that this comparison excludes manufacturing and processing expenses.

The numerical analysis results confirm that increasing the spacing between structural sheets leads to a corresponding rise in maximum vertical displacement. Within Group A, a 125% increase in the d2 spacing in Model A1 relative to the baseline Model A resulted in a 16.25% increase in vertical displacement. In Model A2, where the d1 spacing was increased by 125% compared to Model A, the displacement increased by 40.83%.

A similar trend was observed in Group B. Model B1, with a 111.11% increase in d2 spacing relative to Model B, exhibited a 30.02% increase in displacement. In Model B2, the same percentage increase in d1 spacing led to a significant 98.26% rise in displacement.

3. Conclusions

The results of this study demonstrate that grid spacing has a direct and quantifiable impact on multiple structural response parameters, particularly permanent deformation and plastic strain energy accumulation, under vertical loading conditions. As the lower support spacing (d1) increases, the system exhibits a significantly higher vertical displacement compared to changes in the upper contact spacing (d2), indicating that the lower boundary condition plays a more dominant role in deformation behavior. Specifically, increasing grid spacing from 32 mm to 72 mm led to a 41% increase in deformation for Group A and nearly a 98% increase for Group B. Additionally, the plastic strain energy increased by 28% in Group A and by 66% in Group B. These results indicate not only that larger grid spacing weakens the overall stiffness of the structure, but also that the rate of change in structural responses is non-linear and significant—highlighting the importance of detailed numerical evaluation in design stages.

Although basic theory suggests that increasing spacing would lead to higher deformation, the specific magnitude and rate of increase observed in this study provide valuable design guidance. The finite element simulations further highlight that, beyond a certain spacing threshold, stiffness reduction becomes critical enough to induce excessive permanent deformation, even if plastic energy accumulation may vary. Therefore, in practical FOPS designs, a careful balance must be struck between manufacturing feasibility (e.g., grid spacing or plate thickness) and the protective performance of the structure.

Future studies should investigate failure risks such as fracture initiation or buckling under impact conditions, to complement the current deformation- and energy-based findings. Nonetheless, this study offers a quantified insight into how grid design parameters influence protective cabin structures, serving as a basis for optimization in real-world applications.

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References

- [1] ISO 3471:2008, Earth-moving machinery - Roll-over protective structures - Laboratory tests and performance requirements
- [2] ISO 3449:2005, Earth-moving machinery - Falling-object protective structures - Laboratory tests and performance requirements
- [3] Gomathinayagam, A., Stephen, P. A., Babu, S., & Keshava, K. (2019). Simulation of Falling Object Protective Structure Testing of Earth Moving Equipment Cabin. In *Research into Design for a Connected World: Proceedings of ICoRD 2019 Volume 1* (pp. 203-213). Springer Singapore.
- [4] Pai, K. N. (2006). Modeling of Rollover Protective Structure and Falling Object Protective Structure Tests on a Composite Cab for Skid Steer Loaders (Doctoral dissertation, Wichita State University, College of Engineering).
- [5] Gheorghe, G., Persu, C., Mihai, M., Cujbescu, D., Biris, S., & Maican, E. (2018). Theoretical Simulation for Protective Structure of Operator Cabin Against Falling Object. *46. Symposium "Actual Tasks on Agricultural Engineering"*, Opatija, Croatia, 2018
- [6] Koca Bıyık, K.R. (2010). Bir iş makinesi kabinine uygulanan dinamik analizlerin bilgisayar ortamında simülasyonu Master's thesis, Yıldız Technical University, Istanbul
- [7] Al-Bassit, L., Tricot, N., & Sayegh, S. (2019). Falling-object protective structure for tractors in service: Prototype design and validation. *Biosystems engineering*, vol 185, 76-87.
- [8] Hallén, A., & Hjorth, J. (2022). Development of Methodology for Finite Element Simulation of Overhead Guard Impact Test. Master's thesis, Linköping University, Linköping
- [9] Seshu, P. (2003). *Textbook of finite element analysis*. PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd.
- [10] MSC.Software Corporation, *MSC.Marc volume C: Program Input*, version 2005
- [11] Puso, M., Laursen, T., & Solberg, J. (2004, April). A 3D frictional segment-to-segment contact method for large deformations and quadratic elements. In Published in: *European Congress on Computational Methods in Applied Sciences and Engineering Proceedings*, n/a, n/a, July 28, 2005, pp. 1 (No. UCRL-JRNL-203338). Lawrence Livermore National Lab.(LLNL), Livermore, CA (United States).
- [12] Recuero, A., & Lindsay, A. (2023). On practical aspects of variational consistency in contact dynamics. *Journal of Computational and Nonlinear Dynamics*, 18(8), 081003.
- [13] Metzger, D. R., & Dubey, R. N. (1986). Objective tensor rates and frame indifferent constitutive models. *Mechanics research communications*, 13(2), 91-96.